

In subsequent soil layers, a decreasing trend was also noted but was non-significant. Decrease in soil pH was 0.6, 2.0 and 0.9% in 10-20, 20-30 and 30-50 cm soil layers, respectively. The categorical analysis also revealed the differential effect of various climates, soil textures, duration of the experiment and cropping systems. However, the effect was mostly limited to the surface soil layer. Among the climate, NT reduced the pH by 2.3% under continental climate than CT while it was similar for all other climates. Among the soil texture, medium-textured soils significantly diminished the soil pH by 3.0% while a marginal increase (1.3%) and decrease (0.3%) was noted for fine and coarse-textured soils, respectively. With an increase in the duration of the experiment, the effect of NT on soil pH augmented. The adoption of NT for >20 years caused a 3.4% decrease in soil pH as compared to CT while it was 0.2 ($p > 0.05$) and 0.8% ($p > 0.05$) for <10 and 10-20 yrs duration, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

The global meta-analysis clearly brings out the positive aspects of no-tillage in terms of soil N concentration and stock. Omission of tillage and retention of crop residue increased the soil N concentration of the surface soil and concurrently, soil N stock also increased. Duration of experiment had an explicit role in the extent of N enrichment and an increasing trend was noted with longer duration of NT adoption.

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A birds-eye-view to crop health through unmanned aerial systems (UAS) in agriculture

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Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS)/ Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV), better known as Drones are unmanned aircraft, which are remotely controlled or which can fly autonomously. They are associated with cameras, GPS, and some other sensors, which collect relevant data. Drones in agriculture collect visual images through its camera and the sensors expand the utility of the whole system. Drones collect such information about the crop growth and crop environment, which cannot be observed by farmers' eyes in the visible spectrum, such as a subtle change in moisture content of the soil, crop health, nutrient status of soil, stress condition, crop diseases, etc. (Anonymous 2018). Mapping and imaging capabilities of drone platforms can be used throughout the whole crop season to monitor crop health and collecting other necessary data for better crop production and improved productivity. UAS and advanced image data analysis systems are great tools for the agriculture sector. With the booming of drone industries and image data analysis technology, the use of more appropriate sensors,

high-resolution cameras, and much improved data processing systems are being included along with huge concern on optimization of cost and maximization of utility. Drones inform farmers with more accurate data and help them to maximize yield to their natural limits.

METHODOLOGY

Multispectral and hyper-spectral aerial imagery help to create Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) maps, which is a simple graphical indicator used to analyze remote sensing measurements, assessing whether the object being observed contains live green vegetation or not. By using NDVI, we can estimate the large number of vegetation properties like Leaf Area Index, biomass, chlorophyll content, plant productivity, accumulated rainfall, fractional vegetative cover, differentiation of soil from plants, detect plant under stress, the difference between different crop stages, etc. (Anonymous 2018). It can also detect moisture stress or excess, nutrient deficiencies, crop diseases, pest

infestations. This will help to track problems early and get a better crop yield. Advanced NDVI products can also estimate the loss occurred through natural disaster by comparing pre-disaster state of vegetation to the post-disaster state. Precise documentation of reduction in estimated yield can be used for insurance purposes. Soil quality along with its moisture status can be assessed through 3D imagining and mapping of the terrain. Drone-enabled NDVI system helps to decide proper harvesting time. Drones are very useful in remote areas and plantations and forest areas. Chlorophyll is the substance that reflects nearinfrared lights and this helps to collect precise data for analysis. The basic principle behind NDVI is that due to spongy layers in healthy live plant leaf reflects a lot of light in near infrared in comparison with other non-living objects around the leaf. On the other hand, in the dehydrated stress leaves, the spongy layer subsides and reflects less near infrared light. The colors in the map vary and indicate crop health as dark green/blue for areas with most vegetation and red for least healthy or unhealthy vegetation. According to the formula, NDVI is equal to the difference between intensities of reflected light in the red and the infrared range divided by the sum of those intensities. A very small value (0.1 or less) of NDVI indicates snow, rock, and sand areas. A moderate value of 0.2 to 0.3 indicates shrubs and meadows. A large value like 0.6 to 0.8 represents dense vegetation like temperate and tropical forests. This index value ranges from -1 to +1. According to that scale, farmers can identify which places in the map are indicating heavy biomass and which areas are having less vegetation. Not only in the case of crops, but high-resolution infrared camera can also do sophisticated work like focusing on each and every animal of a herd and can assess its health allowing identification and treatment of the ill animals. Drones with more advanced technology have autopilot unit, radio link, and Ground Control Station Software and flight planning so that even if the drone gets lost in its path, the collected data will not be destroyed. All the recorded data will be saved in an autopilot chipset and those can be downloaded easily on a ground station computer (Mahajan *et al.*, 2016).

RESULTS

Agriculturists are always finding a cost-effective way of crop management strategy to monitor the crops and drones are an important tool for satisfying this need. Farmers can

manage crop issues locally through drone mapping with infrared sensors. In the coming few years, nearly 80 % of the agricultural market will be comprised of drones (Ahiwar *et al.*, 2019). Unmanned aerial vehicles can help in crop monitoring, crop health assessment, crop spraying, planting, soil and field analysis, etc. Since monitoring and mapping of vegetation work with big data image processing, the whole process may use multiple pixels, but the mean can be calculated by the mean of NDVI values for each pixel. Thus, it becomes much easier to handle but during the assessment scale of analysis should be maintained carefully. Many researches are already done and yet proceeding to make drones more accurate, easier to use, more cost-effective, even some researchers are trying to use normal RGB cameras to make it cost less but get results similar to that of multispectral cameras.

CONCLUSION

The future of UAVs in precision agriculture is lying on the farmers' hands, who are interested in adopting new technologies for themselves. Proper training and awareness should be spread among the farmers. Continuous research, innovations, and advancement in technology will make this system more common to farmers. It may look like a good amount of investment, but in long term, it is beneficial as it will give more precision and accuracy to crop information and will increase ultimate crop yield. The outcome for using drones as a site-specific precision tool is encouraging development in the agricultural field.

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